

накопичувачів енергії. У середньостроковій перспективі слід також активізувати реінжиніринг існуючих програм, таких як «Енергодім» і проекти GIZ, адаптуючи їх до викликів війни та потреб відбудови на принципах енерго- та ресурсної стійкості.

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DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN'S ENTREPRENEURSHIP – THE KEY TO A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY

Abstract: This article is dedicated to a modern area of entrepreneurial development — women's entrepreneurship. Global trends show a growing interest in this topic. Traditionally, women have been viewed as the keepers of the home, while men were expected to be the primary breadwinners. However, in the 21st century, this perception is changing. By unlocking the great potential of women's entrepreneurship, a multifaceted effect can be achieved: women are able to pursue self-realization and earn additional income, while society benefits from the added value generated through this process.

Keywords: women's entrepreneurship, gender, barriers, prospects.

The relevance of the topic of the study is conditioned by several key aspects related to the prospects for the development of women's entrepreneurship, both in the Republic of Moldova and worldwide.

Women constitute a significant part of the able-bodied population of the Republic of Moldova, but their potential in entrepreneurship has not yet been fully realised. The development of women's entrepreneurship can contribute to increasing the national gross product and improving the economic stability of the country. Supporting women in business contributes to their social activation and integration, which is an important factor in combating gender stereotypes and improving the status of women in society.

The women's business sector is often oriented towards social and educational projects, as well as innovations in traditional industries, which contributes to the overall technological and social development of the country.

Interest in women's entrepreneurship is growing not only in the Republic of Moldova, but also worldwide. The topic of women's entrepreneurship is actively supported by international organisations such as the UN, the World Bank, which opens additional opportunities for financial and advisory support in the Republic of Moldova.

According to the Government Decision of the Republic of Moldova No. 809 of 27-10-2023 “On Approval of the Programme for Supporting Women’s Entrepreneurship”:

✓ Women’s entrepreneurship refers to the activity of starting and/or managing and developing a business by women for the purpose of generating profit and contributing to economic development;

✓ Woman entrepreneur means a woman who starts and/or organizes a business, manages it, and develops it;

✓ Aspiring woman entrepreneur refers to a woman who is engaging in entrepreneurial activity for the first time and/or does not hold control or a share of at least 51% in a business that has been operating for more than 24 months [1].

Women's entrepreneurship development not only contributes to economic growth and development, but also plays an important role in the struggle for gender equality. Women entrepreneurs often face particular challenges, such as limited access to finance, resources and support networks, as well as societal and cultural stereotypes about women's roles in business. Despite these challenges, many women successfully launch and grow their businesses, making significant contributions to the economy and society [2,3,4].

Another definition of women's entrepreneurship is a *business that is led by women*. Despite making up half of the world's population and 47% of the labour force, women are still underrepresented in the top echelons of business. Global statistics estimate that women's presence in business is severely inferior to men, as the following figures eloquently illustrate [6]:

- Only 5% of the richest billionaires are women,
- Only 6% of S&P 500 companies are headed by women,
- 20% of board members of Fortune 500 companies are women.

A large number of arguments can be made against reducing the existing gap between female and male entrepreneurship, but the most compelling one is that companies with gender diversity have greater performance. In addition, research proves that companies run by women are more efficient [2].

Research also shows that women's entrepreneurship is strongest in the US: more than 30 per cent of small businesses are owned by women, and the number continues to grow. Globally, women own more than a third of all businesses and employ a quarter of all workers. In families with two earning members, about a quarter of women earn more than their husbands. Despite the favorable trends that have emerged, these numbers are still small.

Despite the fact that, according to world statistics, women make up about half of the working-age population, they are underrepresented in all categories of employment statistics. The same is true for entrepreneurship. According to research by the McKinsey Institute, this low participation could cost the economy more than \$28 trillion in unrealised profits, which in turn would reduce global gross domestic product (GDP) by around \$108 trillion in 2025. At the same time, breaking down gender inequality and women's participation in many areas of activity, world GDP could increase to about \$136 trillion by 2025 [8].

Six types of interventions are needed to close the gender gap:

- ✓ financial incentives and support;
- ✓ technology and infrastructure;
- ✓ economic opportunity creation;
- ✓ capacity development;
- ✓ advocacy and attitude formation;
- ✓ laws, policies and regulations.

Among the barriers to female entrepreneurship, the following factors are mainly highlighted: discrimination from the environment; internal barriers such as: fear of leadership or success, especially among women and talented girls; low self-esteem and lack of ambition, exacerbated by a lack of sufficient female role models.

Despite firmly entrenched gender stereotypes, the growing number of women in entrepreneurship may be gradually changing this situation. However, more research is needed to fully explain the gender gap in entrepreneurial activity in at least two dimensions: individual perceptions and environmental influences.

Since the 2000s, the Moldovan government has been actively supporting the development of entrepreneurship, including women's entrepreneurship. This was manifested in the creation of special support, training and microfinance programmes for women. Particular attention has been paid to helping women overcome social and cultural barriers that may prevent them from doing business.

Women's entrepreneurship is a national priority. In the National Development Strategy 'Moldova 2030', the authorities encourage and support women's economic participation and self-employment through capacity and knowledge building measures in entrepreneurship and the development of mentoring services, grants and increased access to credit services. According to the latest data, the share of women entrepreneurs who fully own a business or a larger share - 50% of the business - is about 34% in the

Republic of Moldova. Thus, according to the OECD international community definition, every third entrepreneur in the country is a woman.

Since 2016, the SME Sector Development Strategy for the period 2012-2020 has introduced a separate priority for the development of women's entrepreneurship and a range of measures to support it. In the same year, the Government approved a pilot programme 'Women in Business' aimed at promoting women entrepreneurship and increasing their income and reducing economic disparities between women and men. There are key gender differences in the structure of enterprises by type of economic activity. The share of enterprises in wholesale trade is significantly higher among women entrepreneurs than among men (by about 17.3 %). Also, the share of enterprises owned by women in the service sector (by 4 % more) and in the hotel and restaurant business exceeds the percentage of male-owned enterprises by 1.6%. In the other sectors, the share of male-owned enterprises prevails [7].

National legislation and the strategic framework for gender equality provided for equal access to entrepreneurship and supported the development of women's entrepreneurship and business initiatives. In line with the objectives and national priorities, the development partner community (European Union, European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, World Bank, United Nations, Government of Sweden) has recently supported programmes and initiatives that promote women's involvement in business. A key moment in the development of Moldovan women's entrepreneurship was the Government Decision No. 809 of 27-10-2023 on the approval of the Women's Entrepreneurship Support Programme.

The ODA (Organizația pentru Dezvoltarea Antreprenoriatului) plays a key role in the development and implementation of this programme, having elaborated the Women's Entrepreneurship Support Programme, which 'aims to stimulate and develop businesses run by women'.

According to the vision of the WBA, 'Economic independence and empowerment of women is a key factor in the realisation of their rights and gender equality. This includes the opportunity for equal participation in the labour market and entrepreneurship'.

The main objective of the programme is to provide financial and non-financial support for the development of women's entrepreneurship by increasing the number of women entrepreneurs and improving the economic performance of micro, small and medium enterprises run by women.

In conclusion, the development of women's entrepreneurship in the Republic of Moldova requires a systematic approach and cooperation of various stakeholders, including the government, non-governmental organisations and international partners. Creating a favourable environment for women entrepreneurs not only contributes to economic growth, but also promotes social justice and equality. The implementation of comprehensive support measures aimed at removing existing barriers will significantly increase the level of entrepreneurial activity among women and create prerequisites for sustainable development of the country's economy.

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